

New Developments in Structure/Property Relationships: Relating Fluid Ingress to mechanical and thermal properties

W. Tian*, B. Dao and R. Varley
CSIRO Materials Science and Engineering
Clayton VIC 3169 Australia

* Corresponding author (Wendy.Tian@csiro.au)

Keywords: epoxy, amine, solvent ingress, structure property relationship

1 Introduction

Structure/property relationships of cured epoxy/amine networks have been widely studied for many years [1-5] and with this knowledge, formulations for high performance composite applications with optimized processing and performance characteristics have been developed. In actual service these materials are always used in harsh environment which lead to their accelerated aging [6-8]. Moisture has been one of the primary concerns and many studies have focused on the effect of various hydrothermal treatment [9-11]. However the structure and property relationship in aggressive environment such as in organic solvent is less studied and not well understood [12-15]. Given the importance of solvent resistance to continued application of composite materials in near engine applications, it was considered important to undertake a systematic study on structure property relationship for a range of epoxy resins and different amine hardeners with a view to better understanding the factors which impact solvent ingress.

This work has therefore prepared a range of epoxy based polymer networks and determined their mechanical (compressive strength, modulus and strain) properties, thermal (glass transition temperature) properties and fluid resistances (MEK uptake) using many emerging amine hardeners and epoxy resins.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

The formulations prepared in this work consisted mostly of three different epoxy resins, namely the commercially available diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (referred to as BisA epoxy) (Dow Australia), diglycidyl ether of bisphenol F (referred to as BisF) (Huntsman, Australia) and the experimental epoxy resin, 1,4-bis(2-(4-(oxiran-2-ylmethoxy) phenyl) propan-2-yl) benzene referred to as BisM epoxy. The amines used were as follows: 4,4 diamino diphenyl sulphone (4,4 DDS), 3,3 diamino diphenyl sulphone, (3,3 DDS) methylene dianiline (MDA), 4,4'-[1,3-Phenylenebis(1-Methyl ethylidene)] Bisaniline (BisM), 4,4'-[1,4-Phenylenebis(1-Methyl-ethylidene)] Bisaniline (BisP) and 1,3-Bis (4-aminophenoxy) benzene (TPE-R). All of the amines were powders while the epoxy resins were high viscosity liquids. All chemicals were used as received, though prior to blending and curing, all chemicals were extensively degassed at elevated temperature. The chemical structures are shown in Figure 1.

2.2 Sample Preparation

The formulations were prepared as follows. The epoxy resins and hardener were placed together in a round bottom flask at a 1:1 epoxide:amino stoichiometry and the mixed using a rotary evaporator until the hardener had fully dissolved into the epoxy resin and the blend was free of bubbles. This continued for approximately

1-2 hrs depending upon the reactivity of the formulation. The resin samples were then poured into pre-heated moulds and cured for 5 hrs at 150°C, followed by 10hrs at 177°C, then allowed to cool down overnight.

2.3 Characterization

Fluid uptake was performed by immersing the samples in methyl ethyl ketone (MEK) in a sealed jar at room temperature. Three cylinder with dimension 15 mm diameter and 15 mm in height were weighed two times per week to quantify fluid ingress which was continued for 31 days. The compression samples were also measured after solvent ingress.

The initial weight (W_i) were taken after samples were dried in vacuum oven for 24 hrs. The percentage of absorbed solvent at time t M_t was calculated from

$$M_t = (W_t - W_i) \times 100\% / W_i$$

Three samples were measured and results were averaged.

Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA) was performed using a Perkin-Elmer SEIKO DMA Diamond II Series. Samples of dimensions 12 mm x 50 mm x 2.8 mm were placed in a dual cantilever fixture and a force amplitude of 20 μ m was applied at a frequency of 1Hz. The glass transition temperature of the network, was measured by performing a temperature ramp from 50°C to 250°C at a rate of 2°C/min.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was performed using a Mettler Toledo DSC821^e in the dynamic modes using, 5-10mg. The sample was placed in a sealed aluminium crucible and placed inside the furnace in nitrogen environment. The sample was heated from 50 °C to 300 °C at a rate of 10°C/min. DSC was used to ensure that the cure profile used had not exothermic transition remaining after cure.

Compressive properties were determined using an Instron 5500R Universal Testing Machine fitted with a 50 kN load cell and flat platens. Cylindrical samples with height to diameter ratio of 1:1 were milled.

Sample were placed between the platens and compressed using a crosshead displacement of 1 mm/min at constant temperature 23°C. Compressive strain to yield, at failure, yield and failure stress and modulus were determined.

This work focusses upon three different epoxy resin, BisA and BisF where the only difference between them is the isopropyl versus methylene linkage between the phenyl groups, and BisM which is in effect an extended or higher molecular weight BisA epoxy. The amine hardeners are grouped into 2 separate experiments, the first explore the impact of different substitution patterns on biphenyl amines as well as the effect of a methylene linkage between the biphenyl groups (set 1). The second experiment uses tri phenyl amines (set 2) and continues to explore the impact of substitution patterns, but also compares the impact of isopropyl versus ether linkages between phenyl groups. The polymer networks are more clearly identified in Table 1.

3 Result and discussion

3.1 Fluid resistance – set 1

The examination of solvent absorption of polymer material is critical because the solvent may plasticize the materials, causing a reduction of T_g and deterioration of mechanical properties. Fig. 2 shows the solvent uptake results plotted as a function change in mass (%) versus time (days) for the epoxy systems cured with 33DDS, 44DDS and MDA. In general, a linear solvent absorption is observed for all the systems studied. The BisA networks irrespective of the hardener increase their mass by between 0.9% and 0.5%, while the BisM networks increase their mass by between 5 and 20%. In fact, most of the BisM epoxy systems disintegrated during MEK immersion and was therefore not able to be measured at all, apart from the BisM- MDA system which shows extremely rapid increase in MEK. The linear mass uptake over time has been reported by others[12, 14]. The significant solvent absorption difference

between the two epoxies is associated with their chemical structures. The extra diphenyl isopropyl unit in BisM contributes to a higher free volume which facilitate molecular diffusion within the resin. [12, 16]

Examining the specific impact of the different hardeners, focusing on the BisA system, showed that the 3,3 DDS was the most resistant to MEK ingress, increasing of the order of 0.5wt%, followed by the MDA cured network, increasing by about 0.65wt% and then the 4,4 DDS network which increased in mass by about 0.85wt% after 31 days soaking. The BisF-MDA system displayed the greatest resistance to solvent ingress that methylene linkages are beneficial for improving fluid resistance.

3.2 Thermal and Mechanical Properties – set 1

Fig. 3a) shows the $\tan\delta$ spectra for some epoxy network, illustrating the reduction in T_g for the MDA and 33DDS cured systems. The difference between 33DDS and 44DDS is clearly a result of the different packing afforded by the kinked structure of the 33DDS. The overall results are shown in Figure 3b) which shows that these trends are evident for all of the resin systems.

The meta vs para substitution from the amine has a substantial impact upon the glass transition temperature. Comparing BisA epoxy cured with the 4,4 DDS with 3,3 DDS the glass transition temperature decreases by 25°C after curing both samples at 177°C for 10 hrs. Since both systems are fully cured, this clearly illustrates the effect of a stiff linear polymer backbone compared with the kinked backbone which surely arises from the 3,3 DDS hardener.

Similarly the T_g results from sample set 2 (Fig. 5) shows, regardless of the epoxy used, either BisA, BisF or BisM, the para substituted amine, BisP increases the T_g compared with the meta substituted amine, BisM. The increase is 25°C for the BisA epoxy resin, 17°C for the BisM epoxy

resin and 17 °C for the BisF epoxy resin. The increase in T_g as a result of the para-substitution averages about 14%.

The BisM structural moiety also reduces the glass transition temperature substantially. In the case of 4,4 DDS, 3,3 DDS and MDA they are reduced by 28, 46.2 and 20.8 °C respectively. This is presumably a direct result of the higher molecular weight of the BisM group, but further highlights the impact on the glass transition of meta- substitution. Also of note is that this occurs even though the meta- substitution occurs at the core of the molecule. Also of interest is that the already meta substituted 3,3 DDS has an exaggerated reduction in glass transition temperature, suggestive of a synergistic reduction in glass transition temperature.

The compressive properties are shown in Figure 4 and illustrate the impact of the kinked backbone from the 3,3 DDS to cure the epoxy network. There is a marked increase in modulus compared with the corresponding 4,4 DDS cured networks. This was observed for both the BisA and BisM systems. Modulus as a property is well known to be controlled by short range molecular motions, that is related to molecular packing, and free volume related matters[1, 17] , so it is perhaps not surprising that the kinked polymer network might facilitate improved molecular packing, reduced free volume and hence higher modulus. This effect was exacerbated for the BisM polymer network most likely because it contains greater levels of meta- substitution already within the epoxy component of the structure and therefore increased kinking in the backbone structure.

Figure 4b) shows the yield stress and strain results, which that BisA tends to have higher properties than BisM indicative of the importance of crosslink density on these properties.

3.2 Fluid resistance – set 2

Figure 5 shows the fluid resistance for the tri aromatic amine cured with the three different epoxy resins. Comparing the two plots 5a) and b) which show the impact of BisA versus BisF, it is clear that BisF with its methylene linkages displays significantly improved behaviour, but again, any resin system that has the consecutive isopropyl species displays very poor fluid resistance. Other points to note are that BisP amine is generally poorer than the BisM amine again reflecting the likely increased free volume for a more rigid linear structure compared with the flexible and kinked BisM structure amine. The TPE-R hardener with multiple ether linkages however, displayed superior performance regardless of whether it was cured with the BisF or BisA epoxy resins.

3.3 Thermal and Mechanical Properties

The glass transition temperatures as determined from the $\tan\delta$ spectra are shown in Figure 6 which show that the BisP, para substituted amine, with a more linear structure, imparts a higher T_g than the BisM and TPE-R which are more kinked and flexible. The epoxy resin used is also shown to be important in controlling the T_g of the final network. BisA affords the highest T_g , followed by the BisF then the BisM. The lowest T_g for the BisM epoxy is expected because of the low crosslink density, however, the BisF epoxy with its methylene linkages clearly has greater flexibility compared with the BisA epoxy.

The compressive mechanical properties in Figure 6 illustrate again this balance of flexibility and free volume within the structure and its impact upon properties. Figure 6a) shows the modulus, which is more controlled by short range motions. Here the BisM network is revealed to have higher properties compared with the BisF and BisA, in direct contrast to the T_g measurements. Overall the results, again correspond to increased levels of flexibility in the structure allowing greater

packing and hence less free volume. Of particular note is the BisM epoxy- BisM amine system which has the highest modulus. In contrast, the BisA-BisP amine network has the lowest, given that it was shown to have the highest T_g and hence, likely the most rigid and therefore poorly packed network. The yield stress and strain plot shown in Figure 6b) however, show the opposite behaviour, being more in accordance with cross link densities as would be expected.

4 Discussion

This study has systematically varied the structure of polymer networks via altering the structure of both the epoxy and amine component. Some structure/property relationships identified in this work are as follows:

- Increasing the molecular weight of the isopropyl diphenyl repeat unit within the epoxy resin:
 - a. Decreases T_g for the di-, and tri- aromatic rings, but more so for the di- aromatic amine.
 - b. Enormously reduces solvent resistance. The BisM epoxy either dissolves or causes massive MEK uptake.
- Changing amine substitution from para- to meta- for di- and tri- aromatic amines:
 - a. Meta substitution of the DDS greatly reduces. More so when used in conjunction with the BisM epoxy.
 - b. Irrespective of epoxy resin, meta substitution increases modulus, due to improved packing afforded by the kinked structure.
 - c. Increases solvent resistance for 3,3 DDS compared with 4,4 DDS, due to better packing and reduced free volume.
 - d.
- Comparison of isopropyl versus ether linkages:
 - a. Irrespective of epoxy resin, isopropyl linkages, increase modulus.

- b. For the BisA and BisF epoxy resin, the isopropyl linkages, reduce MEK resistance.

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Figure 1. Chemical structures of the epoxy resins and amine hardeners used in this work.

Figure 2. MEK fluid uptake in epoxy resins (BisA, BisF, BisM) cured with 3,3DDS, 4,4DDS and MDA as a function of time at room temperature.

Figure 3 a) tan delta spectra of the mechanical analysis of BisA cured with 3,3DDS, 4,4DDS and MDA showing and b) the Tgs as a function of epoxy resin and curing agent.

Figure 4 Impact on varying polymer network structure on a) modulus and b) yield stress and strength.

Figure 5 MEK fluid uptake at room temperature for a) BisA (and one BisM epoxy resin) and b) BisF epoxy resins cured with BisP, BisM and TPE-R

Figure 6 Tgs of the polymer networks produced from curing BisA, BisF and BisM epoxy resins with BisM, TPE-R and BisP amine hardeners.

Figure 7. Impact on network structure on a) modulus and b) yield stress and strength for BisA, BisF and BisM epoxy resins cured with BisM, BisP and TPE-R amine hardeners.

Table 1. Samples prepared

Epoxy resin	Amine Hardener	
	Set 1	Set 2
BisA, BisF, BisM	3,3DDS	BisM-amine
	4,4DDS	BisP-amine
	MDA	TPE-R-amine